

Software Development Technology Productivity – Experiment protocol – part I (software application creation)

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Contents:

1.	Introduction.....	3
2.	Functional Model.....	4
2.1	Package: Authentication (P1).....	4
2.2	Package: User Management (P2).....	4
2.3	Package: Project and Task Management (P3).....	5
3.	Use Case Specifications.....	6
3.1	Package: User Authentication (P1).....	6
3.1.1	Login (UC1.1).....	6
3.1.2	Password Recovery (UC1.2).....	8
3.1.3	Change Password (UC1.3).....	10
3.1.4	Logout (UC1.4).....	12
3.2	Package: User Management (P2).....	13
3.2.1	List Users (UC2.2).....	13
3.2.2	Create User (UC2.1).....	14
3.2.3	Edit User (UC2.3).....	16
3.3	Package: Project Management (Projects) (P3).....	18
3.3.1	List Projects (UC3.2).....	18
3.3.2	Create Project (UC3.1).....	20
3.3.3	Edit Project (UC3.3).....	22
3.3.4	List Project Tasks (UC3.7).....	24
3.3.5	Create Project Task (UC3.6).....	26
3.3.6	Edit Project Task (UC3.9).....	28

3.3.7	Delete Project Task (UC3.10)	30
3.3.8	List Project Collaborators (UC3.5).....	31
3.3.9	Add Project Collaborator (UC3.4).....	32
3.4	Package: Project Management (Tasks) (P3).....	34
3.4.1	List Collaborator Tasks (UC3.8)	34
4.	Structural Model (Data Model).....	36

1. Introduction

The software application to be developed, named Easy Management, aims to support project management.

The application includes the management of users, projects, and tasks. It is designed to be a Web application and should be compatible with different browsers.

The application has three actors:

- The **Administrator**, who can manage the users of the application;
- The **Project Manager**, who can create projects and project tasks. They can also list, edit and archive their own projects and tasks;
- The **Collaborator**, who can consult and edit tasks via assignment by the Project Manager. They can also view the projects of the tasks they were assigned to.

The software consists of three modules (packages), as depicted in Figure 1: Authentication (P1); User Management (P2); Project and Task Management (P3).

Figure 1. Packages

2. Functional Model

2.1 Package: Authentication (P1)

Figure 2 shows the use cases of the *Authentication* module (package P1).

Figure 2. Use case diagram – Authentication (P1)

2.2 Package: User Management (P2)

Figure 3 shows the use cases of the *User Management* module (package P2).

Figure 3. Use case diagram – User Management (P2)

2.3 Package: Project and Task Management (P3)

Figure 4 shows the use cases of the *Project and Task Management* module (package P3).

Figure 4. Use case diagram – Project and Task Management (P3)

3. Use Case Specifications

3.1 Package: User Authentication (PI)

3.1.1 Login (UC1.1)

The page snapshot shown in Figure 5 is the first to be presented (when a user accesses the application). On this page, the user should enter their access credentials (“email” and “password”). Note that the users are created by the Administrator, and there is no feature for self-registration. The specification of the use case is shown in Table 1.

Figure 5. Login

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Software Development Technology Productivity – Experiment protocol – part I

Table 1. Login

UC1.1	Login
Description: This use case allows a user to sign in to the application.	
Pre-conditions: -	
Main Flow: 1. The “Login” form is shown. 2. The user enters their credentials. 3. The user clicks the “Login” button. A1. The user enters the wrong credentials. A2. The user is not “Active”.	
Alternative flows: A1. The user enters the wrong credentials. 1. An error message is displayed: “Invalid email or password”. 2. The flow returns to step 2 of the Main Flow. - A2. The user is not “Active”. 1. An error message is displayed: “Inactive user”. 2. The flow returns to step 2 of the Main Flow.	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: The user becomes authenticated. The user record is updated (entity “User”, column “LastLogin” = login date/time).	

3.1.2 Password Recovery (UC1.2)

If the user forgets their credentials, they can recover the password. For that, they will have to click on the “Forgot your password?” link on the “Login” page (see Figure 5), and then they will be presented with the form shown in Figure 6. After entering the email address and submitting the form, they will receive an email with instructions and a link to recover the password. The specification of the use case is displayed in Table 2.

The image shows a web interface for password recovery. At the top, there is a dark blue header with the text "Easy Management" in white. Below this is a large blue area containing a white rounded rectangle form. The form has the following elements:

- Title:** "Password Recovery" in blue text.
- Instructions:** "Please, fill in your email address, so a recovery email can be sent to you." in grey text.
- Input Field:** A white rounded rectangle with a grey user icon on the left and the label "Email" in grey text.
- Submit Button:** A blue rounded rectangle with the text "Send" in white.

Figure 6. Password Recovery

Table 2. Password Recovery

UC1.2	Password Recovery
Description: The use case allows the user to recover their password.	
Pre-conditions: The user is on the “Login” page.	
Main Flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. On the “Login” page, the user selects the “Forgot your password?” option. 2. The form “Password recovery” is displayed. 3. The user inserts their email address. 4. The user clicks the “Submit” button. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A1. The user enters the wrong email. 5. The user receives an email to define a new password. 6. The user clicks on the link in the email, which opens a new a page with a form to set a new password. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A2. The user does not receive the email or does not click the link. 7. INCLUDE (UC1.3. Change Password) 	
Alternative flows: A1. The user enters the wrong email. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. An error message is displayed: “Invalid email”. 2. The flow returns to step 3 of the Main Flow. - A2. The user does not receive the email or does not click the link. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The password is not changed. 	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: The user password is updated.	

3.1.3 Change Password (UC1.3)

If the user wants to change their password, they must select the “Password Recovery” option (see Section 3.1.2), and then an email is sent with a link to open the form shown in Figure 7. The specification of the use case is shown in Table 3.

The image shows a web interface for changing a password. At the top, there is a dark blue header with the text "Easy Management" in white. Below the header is a large blue area containing a white rounded rectangle form. The form is titled "Change Password" in blue text. It contains two input fields: "Password" and "Confirm password", both with light blue borders. Below the input fields is a blue button with the text "Save" in white.

Figure 7. Change Password

Table 3. Change Password

UC1.3	Change Password
Description: The use case allows the user to change their password.	
Pre-conditions: The user click on the “Forgot your password?” link received by email.	
Main Flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The “Change Password” form is displayed. 2. The user enters the new password on the “Password” and “Confirm Password” fields. 3. The user clicks the “Save” button. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A1. The user inserts different passwords in the fields. 	
Alternative flows: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A1. The user inserts different passwords in the fields. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. An error message is displayed: “The passwords entered are not the same”. 2. The flow returns to step 3 of the Main Flow. 	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: The user password is updated.	

3.1.4 Logout (UC1.4)

To sign out, the user has to click on a button with an icon similar to the one presented in Figure 8. The button should be placed at the upper right corner of all pages, except for the “Login” page. The specification of the use case is shown in Table 4.

Figure 8. Logout icon

Table 4. Logout

UC1.4	Logout
Description: This use case allows the user to sign out.	
Pre-conditions: The user must be authenticated.	
Main Flow: 1. The user clicks the “Logout” button. 2. The user session is terminated.	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: The user is signed out.	

3.2 Package: User Management (P2)

Only the Administrator will have access to the *User Management* module.

3.2.1 List Users (UC2.2)

To access the users list, the Administrator must click on the “Users” tab on the top menu. Then, they will be redirected to the page that shows the list of users registered in the application, as shown in Figure 9. The specification of the use case is shown in Table 5.

Figure 9. List Users

Table 5. List Users

UC2.2	List Users
Description: This use case allows listing the users registered in the application.	
Pre-conditions: The user must be authenticated and have Administrator permission.	
Main Flow: 1. The user (Administrator) accesses the “Users” tab. 2. The user list is presented.	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: -	

3.2.2 Create User (UC2.1)

To create a new user, the Administrator must first click on the “Users” tab and will then be redirected to the users list. Next, the user has to click on the “Create User” link to be directed to the form shown in Figure 10. In this form, the Administrator should enter the name and email of the new user. In addition, the Administrator can indicate if the user has permission to create new projects (checkbox “Create Projects”) and if the user is active, which allows to access the application (checkbox “Active”). The specification of the use case is shown in Table 6.

The screenshot shows a web application interface for user management. At the top, there is a blue navigation bar with the text "Easy Management" on the left and three tabs: "Projects", "Tasks", and "Users". The "Users" tab is currently selected. On the right side of the navigation bar, there are two icons: a user profile icon and a refresh icon. Below the navigation bar, the breadcrumb "Home / Users / Create User" is visible. The main content area features a white card titled "Create User". Inside the card, there are two text input fields labeled "Name:" and "Email:". Below these fields are two toggle switches. The first toggle is labeled "Create projects" and is currently turned on (blue). The second toggle is labeled "Active" and is also turned on (blue). At the bottom of the card, there are two buttons: a blue "Save" button and a grey "Cancel" button.

Figure 10. Create User

Table 6. Create User

UC2.1	Create User
Description: This use case allows creating a new user.	
Pre-conditions: The user must be authenticated and have Administrator permission.	
Main Flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user (Administrator) accesses the “Create User” option on the “Users” tab. 2. A form for creating a new user is displayed. 3. The user (Administrator) fills in the form. 4. The user (Administrator) clicks on the “Save” button. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A1. The user (Administrator) clicks on the “Cancel” button. A2. The form has errors. 	
Alternative flows: A1. The user (Administrator) clicks on the “Cancel” button. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The form for user creation is closed and the user list is displayed (without saving the form data). - A2. The form has errors. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A message is displayed identifying the errors that occurred when filling in the form (e.g., “name not filled in”, “name already exists”, “email not filled in”, “email already exists”, “invalid email”). 2. The flow returns to step 3 of the Main Flow. 	
Exceptions: E1. The user (Administrator) can leave the form without saving.	
Post-Conditions: A new user is created. The user list page is displayed.	

3.2.3 Edit User (UC2.3)

To edit the data of an existing user, the Administrator must first click on the “Users” tab and will then be redirected to the users list. Next, the Administrator must select the user he wants to edit. The Administrator will then be redirected to the form shown in Figure 11. The specification of the use case is shown in Table 7.

The screenshot shows a web application interface with a blue header. The header contains the text "Easy Management" on the left, and navigation tabs for "Projects", "Tasks", and "Users" in the center. On the right side of the header, there are icons for a user profile and a search function. Below the header, the breadcrumb "Home / Users / Create User" is visible. The main content area features a white box titled "Edit User". Inside this box, there are four input fields: "Name:" with the value "user1 name", "Email:" with the value "user1@email.com", "Create projects" with a blue toggle switch turned on, and "Active" with a blue toggle switch turned on. At the bottom of the form, there are two buttons: a blue "Save" button and a grey "Cancel" button.

Figure 11. Edit User

Table 7. Edit User

UC2.3	Edit User
Description: This use case allows editing user details.	
Pre-conditions: The user must be authenticated and have Administrator permission.	
Main Flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user (Administrator) accesses the “Users” tab, where they select the user to be edited by clicking on their name. 2. A form is displayed for editing the user’s data, pre-filled with the data registered in the application. 3. The user (Administrator) makes the necessary changes. 4. The user (Administrator) clicks on the “Save” button. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A1. The user (Administrator) clicks on the “Cancel” button. A2. The form has errors. 	
Alternative flows: A1. The user (Administrator) clicks on the “Cancel” button. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user edit form is closed and the user list page is displayed (without saving the form data). - A2. The form has errors. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A message is displayed identifying the errors detected when filling in the form (e.g., “name not filled in”, “name already exists”, “email not filled in”, “email already exists”, “invalid email”). 2. The flow returns to step 3 of the Main Flow. 	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: The user data is updated. The user list page is displayed.	

3.3 Package: Project Management (Projects) (P3)

3.3.1 List Projects (UC3.2)

To access the projects list, the user needs to click on the “Projects” tab on the taskbar, which will redirect him to the page shown in Figure 12. To search the projects list, the user must enter an expression (referring at least part of the name of the project to be found) in the “Search” textbox and click the “Search” button, and only the projects whose name contains the expression entered in the textbox will be shown. The “Clear” button deletes the text entered in the “Search” textbox, and all projects are listed again. The specification of the use case is shown in Table 8.

Figure 12. List Projects

Table 8. List Projects

UC3.2	List Projects
Description: This use case allows listing and searching the existing projects assigned to the user.	
Pre-conditions: The user must be authenticated.	
Main Flow: 1. The user accesses the “Projects” tab. A1. Filters projects. 2. The list of projects associated with the user is displayed.	
Alternative flows: A1. Filter Projects 1. The user enters an expression referring at least part of the project’s name in the “Search” textbox. 2. The user clicks on the “Search” button. 3. The entered expression is applied as a filter in the project listing. 4. The flow returns to step 2 of the Main Flow.	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: -	

3.3.2 Create Project (UC3.1)

To create a new project, whose form is shown in Figure 13, the user must click on the link “Create” available on the “List Projects” page (see Figure 12). To create a project, the user needs to enter the project’s code (ID), name, and a description, the project’s start and end dates, the project’s status (which can assume the following values: “Not Started”, “In Progress”, “Pending”, and “Complete”), the estimated effort (in minutes), and the actual project effort (in minutes). The use case specification is shown in Table 9.

The screenshot shows a web application interface for creating a project. The header is blue with the text "Easy Management" and navigation tabs for "Projects", "Tasks", and "Users". A breadcrumb trail reads "Home / Projects / Create Project". The main content area is titled "Create Project" and contains the following form elements:

- ID:
- Name:
- Description:
- Start Date: (with a calendar icon)
- End Date: (with a calendar icon)
- Status: (with a dropdown arrow)
- Estimated Effort (Minutes):
- Actual Effort (Minutes):

At the bottom of the form are two buttons: "Save" (blue) and "Cancel" (grey).

Figure 13. Create Project

Table 9. Create Project

UC3.1	Create Project
Description: This use case allows creating a new project.	
Pre-conditions: The user must be authenticated and have Project Manager permission.	
Main Flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user accesses the “Projects” tab. 2. Clicks on “Create”. 3. A form is displayed for filling in. 4. The user fills in and submits the form. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A1. The user clicks on the “Cancel” button. A2. The form has errors. 	
Alternative flows: A1. The user clicks on the “Cancel” button. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The form is closed and the list projects page is displayed (without saving the form data). - A2. The form has errors. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A message is displayed identifying the errors found when filling in the form (e.g., “ID not filled in”, “ID already exists”, “name not filled in”, “name already exists”). All fields are mandatory, except description and actual effort. 2. The flow returns to step 4 of the Main Flow. 	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: The new project is registered. The list projects page is displayed.	

3.3.3 Edit Project (UC3.3)

To access the edit project page (see Figure 14), the user will first need to access the project list page (see Figure 12) and select the project to be edited. This page has two distinct areas: the first one, on the left side, lists all the projects that the user is associated with, allowing the user to select the project they want to view or edit; and the second one, on the right side, has three tabs that allow access to three distinct areas of the project: information, tasks, and collaborators. The use case specification is shown in Table 10.

The screenshot displays the 'Project 1' edit interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Easy Management' and tabs for 'Projects', 'Tasks', and 'Users'. The breadcrumb trail shows 'Home / Projects / Projects Details'. The main content area is titled 'Project 1' and features three tabs: 'Informations', 'Tasks', and 'Collaborators'. The 'Informations' tab is selected, revealing a 'Project Information' form. This form includes input fields for Name, Code, Start Date, End Date, Estimated Effort, Actual Effort, and Status. A large text area for Description is located below these fields. To the left of the form, a section titled 'My Projects:' contains three checkboxes: 'Project 1' (checked), 'Project 2', and 'Project 3'. At the bottom of the form are 'Save' and 'Cancel' buttons.

Figure 14. Project (Informations tab)

Table 10. Edit Project

UC3.3	Edit Project
Description: This use case allows changing the data of a project.	
Pre-conditions: The user must be authenticated and have Project Manager permission.	
Main Flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user accesses the "Projects" tab. 2. The user selects the project they want to edit. 3. The project data is presented. 4. The user makes changes in the project data. 5. The user clicks on the "Save" button. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A1. The form has errors. A2. The project is saved with the status "Archive". 	
Alternative flows: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A1. The form has errors. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A message is displayed identifying the errors when filling in the form. 2. The flow returns to step 4 of the Main Flow. - A2. The project is saved with the status "Archive". <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user is asked if they are sure they want to save this change to the project. 2. If confirmed, the project is updated. 3. If not confirmed, the changes are canceled and the flow returns to step 4 of the Main Flow. 	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: The project data is updated. The list projects page is displayed.	

3.3.4 List Project Tasks (UC3.7)

By clicking on the “Tasks” tab, the user accesses the list of tasks associated with the project selected in "My Projects" (see Figure 15). The user can create a new task (by clicking on the button “Create Task”) or edit an extant task (by clicking on the desired task). In addition to creating or editing the task, the user can delete a task by clicking on the "Waste bin" button displayed in front of each task. The specification of the use case is shown in Table 11.

The screenshot shows a web application interface for 'Easy Management'. The top navigation bar is blue and contains the text 'Easy Management' on the left, and 'Projects', 'Tasks', and 'Users' as tabs in the center. On the right of the navigation bar are icons for a user profile and a search function. Below the navigation bar, the breadcrumb 'Home / Projects / Projects Details' is visible. The main content area is titled 'Project 1' and features three tabs: 'Informations', 'Tasks' (which is selected and highlighted in blue), and 'Collaborators'. To the right of these tabs is a 'Create Task' button. On the left side of the 'Tasks' tab, there is a 'My Projects:' section with three radio buttons: 'Project 1' (checked), 'Project 2', and 'Project 3'. The main part of the 'Tasks' tab displays a table with the following structure:

Task	Code	Description	Status	
Task 1	Code	Description	Status	
Task 2	Code	Description	Status	
Task 3	Code	Description	Status	
Task 4	Code	Description	Status	
Task 5	Code	Description	Status	

Figure 15. Project (Tasks tab)

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Table 11. List Project Tasks

UC3.7	List Project Tasks
Description: This use case allows the user to list the tasks that are associated with a project.	
Pre-conditions: The user must be authenticated.	
Main Flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The user accesses the "Tasks" tab.2. If the user is the Project Manager:<ol style="list-style-type: none">2.1. The list of tasks associated with the project is displayed.3. Otherwise (Collaborator):<ol style="list-style-type: none">3.1. The list of the user's tasks associated with the project is displayed.	
Alternative flows: -	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: -	

3.3.5 Create Project Task (UC3.6)

To access the “Create Task” functionality, the user must click on the button in the upper right corner on the “List Tasks” page (see Figure 15) and will then be redirected to a page that allows the creation of tasks (see Figure 16). This form displays several fields, namely code, name, status ("Not Started", "In Progress", "Pending" and "Complete"), the collaborator that will perform the task, a brief description, the task's start date and expected end date, as well as the estimated and actual effort in executing the task (in minutes). Some of the values of these fields, such as task status, will be updated during the task's execution. The use case specification is shown in Table 12.

The screenshot shows a web application interface for creating a task. The top navigation bar is blue and contains the text "Easy Management" on the left, and "Projects", "Tasks", and "Users" in the center. On the right of the navigation bar are icons for a user profile and a search function. Below the navigation bar, the breadcrumb "Home / Projects / Projects Details" is visible. The main content area is titled "Project 1" and contains a form with three tabs: "Informations", "Tasks", and "Collaborators". The "Tasks" tab is selected. The form is titled "Create Task" and contains the following fields: "Code:" (text input), "Name:" (text input), "Status:" (dropdown menu), "Description:" (text area), "Start Date:" (date picker), "End Date:" (date picker), "Estimated Effort (Minutes):" (text input), and "Actual Effort (Minutes):" (text input). At the bottom of the form are "Save" and "Cancel" buttons. On the left side of the form, there is a section titled "My Projects:" with three checkboxes: "Project 1" (checked), "Project 2", and "Project 3".

Figure 16. Create Project Task

Table 12. Create Project Task

UC3.6	Create Project Task
Description: This use case allows creating a new project task.	
Pre-conditions: The user must be authenticated and have Project Manager permission.	
Main Flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user selects "Create Task". 2. A form is displayed to fill in the task details. 3. The user fills in and submits the form. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A1. The user clicks on the "Cancel" button. A2. The form has errors. 	
Alternative flows: A1. The user clicks on the "Cancel" button. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The form is closed and the list tasks page is displayed (without saving the form data). - A2. The form has errors. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A message identifying the errors found when filling in the form is displayed. 2. The flow returns to step 3 of the Main Flow. 	
Exceptions:	
Post-Conditions: A new task is registered. The list tasks page is displayed.	

3.3.6 Edit Project Task (UC3.9)

To access the “Edit Task” functionality, the user must select a task from the task list and will then be redirected to the task viewing/editing page (see Figure 17). After changing the fields, the user must click on the “Save” button to submit the changes made. The specification of the use case is shown in Table 13.

The screenshot displays the 'Easy Management' web application interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Easy Management', 'Projects', 'Tasks', and 'Users', along with user profile and navigation icons. The breadcrumb trail shows 'Home / Projects / Projects Details'. The main content area is titled 'Project 1' and features three tabs: 'Informations', 'Tasks', and 'Collaborators'. The 'Tasks' tab is active, showing an 'Edit Task' form. On the left, a 'My Projects' section lists 'Project 1' (checked), 'Project 2', and 'Project 3'. The 'Edit Task' form includes fields for Code, Name, Status (dropdown), Description, Start Date, End Date, Estimated Effort (Minutes), and Actual Effort (Minutes). A 'Save' button and a 'Cancel' button are located at the bottom of the form.

Figure 17. Edit Project Task

Table 13. Edit Project Task

UC3.9	Edit Project Task
Description: This use case allows the user to edit a project task.	
Pre-conditions: The user must be authenticated.	
Main Flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user selects, from the list of tasks, the task they wish to edit. 2. A form is displayed with the details of the task. 3. The user fills in and submits the form. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A1. The user clicks on the “Cancel” button. A2. The form has errors. 	
Alternative flows: A1. The user clicks on the "Cancel" button. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The form is closed and the list project tasks page is displayed (without saving the form data). - A2. The form has errors. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A message is displayed identifying the errors found when filling in the form (e.g., "code not filled in", "code already exists", "name not filled in", "name already exists"). All fields are mandatory, except description, actual effort, and collaborator. 2. The flow returns to step 3 of the Main Flow. 	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: The task data is updated. The list project tasks page is displayed.	

3.3.7 Delete Project Task (UC3.10)

To delete a task of a project, the user must click on the “Waste bin” button in front of a particular task in the “List project Tasks” page. The use case specification is in Table 14.

Table 14. Delete Project Task

UC3.10	Delete Project Task
Description: This use case allows the user to delete a task.	
Pre-conditions: The user must be authenticated and have Project Manager permission.	
Main Flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user clicks on the "Delete Task" icon. 2. The system asks if the user really wants to perform this action. 3. The user confirms the deletion. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A1. The user cancels the deletion. 	
Alternative flows: A1. The user clicks on the “Cancel” button. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The form is closed, and the list project tasks page is displayed (without saving the form data). 	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: The task is deleted. The list project tasks page is displayed.	

3.3.8 List Project Collaborators (UC3.5)

To view the collaborators associated with a project, the user needs to click on the "Collaborators" tab and, a page with a list of the collaborators will be displayed (see Figure 18). At the top of the list, on the right side, is the option “Add Collaborator”, which allows adding a new collaborator to the selected project. The use case specification is shown in Table 15.

Figure 18. Project (Collaborators tab)

Table 15. List Project Collaborators

UC3.5	List Project Collaborators
Description: This use case is only available to the Project Manager and allows viewing the collaborators associated with a project.	
Pre-conditions: The user must be authenticated.	
Main Flow: 1. The user accesses the “Collaborators” tab. 2. The list of collaborators/users associated with the project is displayed.	
Alternative Flows: -	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: -	

3.3.9 Add Project Collaborator (UC3.4)

This use case enables the selection of collaborators to be added to a project, allowing tasks to be assigned subsequently (Figure 19). The use case specification is shown in Table 16.

Figure 19. Add Project Collaborator

Table 16. Add Project Collaborator

UC3.4	Add Project Collaborator
Description: This use case is only available to the Project Manager and allows adding collaborators to the project.	
Pre-conditions: The user must be authenticated.	
Main Flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user clicks on the "Collaborators" tab on the project page. 2. The user selects the collaborator to be added and clicks on the "Add" button. A1. The user clicks on the "Cancel" button. 3. The user is redirected to the collaborator list page. 	
Alternative flows: A1. The user clicks on the "Cancel" button. 1. The form is closed, and the list project collaborators page is displayed (without saving the form data).	
Exceptions:	
Post-Conditions: The collaborator is added to the project. The list of project collaborators page is displayed.	

3.4 Package: Project Management (Tasks) (P3)

3.4.1 List Collaborator Tasks (UC3.8)

The "Tasks" tab allows the collaborator to access their tasks whose status is not "Complete" (see Figure 20). It is displayed a dashboard of the tasks to be performed by the user, with the possibility to filter by name the tasks displayed. On this page, the user has the options to create a new task (as long as they have Project Manager permission), or view/edit a task by selecting it from the list (see Figure 20). The specification of the use case is shown in Table 17.

Figure 20. List Collaborator Tasks

Table 17. List Collaborator Tasks

UC3.8	List Collaborator Tasks
Description: This use case allows the user to list and filter existing tasks in the application associated with them.	
Pre-conditions: The user must be authenticated.	
Main Flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user accesses the "Tasks" tab. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A1. Filters tasks. 2. The list of the user's tasks is displayed. 	
Alternative flows: A1. Filters tasks <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user enters part of a task name. 2. The system returns the filtered task list. 3. The flow returns to step 2 of the Main Flow. 	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: -	

4. Structural Model (Data Model)

The entity and relationship diagram illustrates the entities relevant to the application and how they relate to each other.

As shown in Figure 21, there are six entities: the User entity, which represents the users of the application; the Project entity, related to the projects managed in the application; the Task entity, which regards to the tasks associated with the projects; the Status entity, which allows defining the status for the projects and tasks (it was decided that projects and tasks would have the same status types); the Profile entity, related to the type of users in the application (currently "Project Manager" and "Collaborator"); and the Project_User entity, which relates the users to the projects, with the specific profiles that the users assume in their projects.

In general, the attributes of the entities presented in Figure 21 are self-explanatory. The exceptions are the following attributes: in the User entity, the attribute CreateProject indicates whether the user can create projects or not; in the User entity, the attribute Active indicates whether the user is active or not (if they are not active, they cannot be authenticated into the application); in the User entity, the attribute SuperUser indicates whether the user is Administrator; in the entities Project and Task, the attributes EstimatedEffort and ActualEffort, represent, respectively, the time expected and the time spent in the execution of the project/task (in minutes).

The following business rule must also be verified: a task is executed by one and only one collaborator.

Figure 21. Entity-Relationship Diagram